

Examining a Community-Based Program for Newly Resettled Refugee Adolescents

Grace H. C. Huang, Monica Miller Marsh, Naila Asad Paul

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to examine refugee-background high school students' experiences in an adolescent support program, Teen Response, and its impact on students' educational and career pathways. Teen Response, offered by a non-profit refugee organization working with a large metropolitan school district and community partners, is in a mid-size midwestern urban community in the United States. Employing a mixed-method approach utilizing surveys and focus groups, we studied nineteen newly resettled refugee-background high school students who participated in the study over nine months. Three overarching themes emerged from the data 1) Teen Response program strategies, 2) growth in self-efficacy, and 3) being an advocate for self and others. This article focuses on the Teen Response program strategies identified as impactful by research participants. It contributes to the knowledge of the design of effective adolescent programs and their impact on refugee-background adolescent development.

Introduction

According to the UNHCR Global Trends Report, more than 100 million people worldwide have been displaced by violence, war, persecution, and human rights abuses by May 2022. Currently, 1 in every 78 people on Earth is displaced (UNHCR, 2022). The number of displaced people has increased every year for the last decade. At the end of 2021, 27.1 million people qualified for refugee status (UNHCR, 2022). The United States has a long history of receiving refugees. While the number of refugees decreased during the former administration, that number has slowly begun to rise. The Biden administration promised 125,000 resettlement places in 2022 (Monin et al., 2021). In his remarks to the United Nations International Migration Review Forum, Secretary of State Antony Blinken affirmed the commitment of the U.S. to working with other countries to pursue solutions to the refugee crisis around the world (Blinken, 2022).

In the U.S., there are many refugee support programs that operate on the local level. These programs connect adult refugees with language and social services and help families access medical care and education for their children. Adolescent refugees are highly affected by the events and stressors specific to their refugee experience (Alharbi, 2018); yet the needs of refugee youth in schools have been largely neglected (Morrice et al., 2020). Thus, supporting youth should be a priority for the host country. In this article, we share how a non-profit refugee organization in a mid-size midwestern urban community worked with a large metropolitan school district and community partners to provide support for refugee adolescents as they seek education and career opportunities in the U.S.

Adolescent Refugees

Adolescence is a unique developmental stage between 11 and 21 years of age. Rapid physical, emotional, cognitive, and social changes occur during this time. These changes include physical and sexual maturation, the development of more abstract and long-term thinking, and an increase in risk-taking behaviors (Soleimanpour et al., 2017) as adolescents move toward independence. Adolescents who are refugees may have more difficulty navigating this stage of life due to the effects of trauma on their cognitive and emotional development. While many refugees exhibit resiliency and adaptability, difficulties around resettlement combined with traumatic experiences before migration can cause significant psychological distress in adolescent refugees (Bronstein & Montgomery, 2011).

Newly resettled adolescent refugees are challenged by a new language, culture, social norms, and resources because they carry different funds of knowledge (Gonzalez et al., 2005; Shaw & Funk, 2019; Wachter et al., 2016). Resettlement challenges, as well as adolescent developmental changes, impact adolescent refugees' learning experiences as they encounter a new set of expectations in terms of cultural knowledge and skills, self-efficacy, pursuit of educational and career pathways, and entrance into the workforce (Alharbi, 2018). Receiving an education is an expectation and high priority for many refugee youth and their families (Dryden-Peterson,

2017; Morrice et al., 2020). Morrice et al. (2020) found that refugee youth are motivated to work hard to reach their educational goals as they understand that an investment in education leads to better job options and a higher quality of life.

Adolescent Refugees and Career Pathways

Refugee adolescents face unique challenges that affect their choices as they set goals and seek opportunities for future careers (McNeely et al., 2017). Psychological stressors of migration and acculturation patterns influence how adolescent refugees know and understand the world and realize new possibilities for their life's path (Ellison, Wohn, & Greenhow, 2014). Yakushko et al. (2008) contend it is essential to teach career options, provide career counseling, discuss with refugee students how to obtain and keep a job, and create workshops and structured groups to instruct and support refugee adolescents as they pursue post-secondary and work options. Yet, there is a paucity of research focused on educational and career planning programs for adolescent refugees (Molla, 2022; Morrice et al., 2020). Entering the workforce would decrease isolation and help build social capital, easing many challenges refugees face in their day-to-day experiences (Yakushko et al., 2008).

In addition to the inherent challenges of this developmental stage, it is crucial to have support and instruction in place in schools for adolescent refugees to advance successfully and avoid feelings of hopelessness and isolation. In a literature review, we found more research on programs offering mental health support to this group (Hettich et al., 2020; Reynolds & Bacon, 2018; Sullivan & Simonson, 2016). Frequently, mental health services are intertwined with educational and career support. The Teen Response Program combines socialemotional support and academic and career support for adolescent refugees.

Teen Response Program

The Teen Response (TR) Program was launched in 2018, with the goal of supporting resettled refugee students in navigating their current high school experience and challenging them to pursue pathways toward educational and career goals. Partnered with a midwestern metropolitan school district, this refugee adolescent program served twenty-six (26) resettled refugee students in one high school. The support services TR provided to student participants included weekly group programming, after-school tutoring, counseling, and career exposure through interactive learning experiences. TR challenged students to explore their interests and aspirations, interface with professionals and employers, and gain awareness of resources for charting their own journey forward.

During the school year, 25 guest speakers from various career fields were invited to discuss their career pathways. Guest speakers introduced and described the professional pathways, preparations, and practices of their fields. Additionally, TR assisted student participants in completing personal development portfolios and secured paid summer internships. In 2019, this cohort group had a 100% high school graduation rate, and 100% of seniors were accepted into post-secondary academic institutions (The Refugee Response, 2019).

The program also involved parents, in order to foster their knowledge about the U.S. school system, educational pathways, as well as awareness of the challenges and opportunities their children may face in society. The goal was to help parents gain confidence in their ability to connect with their children and participate in discussions centered around student experiences and educational pathways. The program offered home visits, parent group, and individual meetings in which students' personal development portfolios were discussed. While family involvement is an important part of TR, for the purposes of this paper, we focus on the student experiences.

Research Methods

Purposes and Research Questions

This paper is part of a larger project that examined adolescent students' experiences and their growth in a pilot support program for resettled refugee high school students. A mixed-method approach was utilized to answer the following two research questions (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Question 1: What were the resettled refugee high school students' experiences and perceptions participating in the Teen Response Program?

Question 2: How did the TR program impact the resettled refugee high school students' educational and career pathways?

In this paper, we focus on research question 2 as we examined the strategies TR program employed to support the participants' educational and career pathways.

Participants

Approximately 86% of the TR program participants have lived in the U.S. three or fewer years and spent three or fewer years in U.S. schools. All students' families had 5 or more children. Most of the families had \$25,000 or lower family annual income (82%) and observed the Muslim faith (86%). As to their ethnic background, approximately 57% of the families were of Syrian/Iraqi descent, following with Sudanese (18%), Congolese (15%), Somali (5%), and Afghan (5%). Table 1 shows the demographics of the TR program participants and their families.

Table 1. Student demographics

Years in the US	Frequency	Percent
2 years	13	59.10%
3 years	6	27.30%
4 years and above	3	13.60%
Household Information	Frequency	Percent
5 children	5	22.70%
6 children	3	13.60%
7 children	3	13.60%
9 children	8	36.40%
10 children	3	13.60%
Family Annual Income	Frequency	Percent
\$25,000 or lower	18	81.80%
\$25,000 or higher	4	18.20%
Religion	Frequency	Percent
Muslim faith	19	86.40%
Catholic faith	1	4.50%
Christian faith	2	9.10%
Ethnicity	Frequency	Percent
Syrian/Iraqi	22	56.40%
Sudanese	7	17.90%
Congolese	6	15.40%
Somali	2	5.10%
Afghan	2	5.10%

Data Collection

Data collection tools included surveys and focus groups conducted throughout the investigation process.

Focus Groups

The primary source of data was semi-structured focus group interviews. A focus group format was utilized to foster openness and collaborative feedback as well as to collect qualitative data regarding participants' perceptions and experiences. Interview questions paralleled those on the surveys and elaborated upon them. All focus groups were audio-recorded and transcribed. All names listed are pseudonyms. Fifteen (15) students participated in four focus groups. Each focus group met for an average time of 1.5 - 2 hours. Focus group questions included the following examples:

- Program highlights: What do you like about this program?
- Learning experiences: One thing you've learned from the program that you didn't know before.
- Did you learn more about yourself after attending TR? What are they? How did TR help?
- What's your future plan (short-term, long-term)?
- When you have questions at school, what do you do? To whom do you go?
- When you have questions about things other than school (e.g. home, work, etc.), what do you do? To whom do you go?
- Educational and career pathways (21 guest speaker session experiences): Which one stood out the most? Why? Did you find it helpful? In what way?
- Did you notice any changes in yourself or others after attending the TR program?
- What is one thing you would like to see change about this program?

Surveys

The second source of data was surveys which were utilized to gain a baseline understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions. The findings were used to complement the open-ended focus group format. There were two surveys conducted, a pre-survey administered in the beginning of the program and a post-survey administered at the end (Teen Response Program Student Survey). The surveys consisted of a 5-point Likert scale. A total of 17 items regarding school engagement, self-efficacy, self-advocacy, and knowledge of career pathways were included (see Table 2). Out of the 26 TR students, 19 students completed both surveys. Survey data was quantitatively analyzed, and descriptive statistics were compiled.

Table 2. Teen Response Program Student Survey (TRPSS) items in four different themes

Theme	Student Response
School Engagement	I have maintained or improved my school attendance since attending TR.
	My GPA has improved or stayed the same since attending TR.
	I reviewed both my current transcript and graduation credit standing with a TR staff or school staff Jan.-May, 2019; Number of Times.
Self-efficacy	I can identify and describe my personal strengths and interests.
	I can identify and describe my academic strengths and interests.
	Since attending TR, I feel better about my life.
Self-advocacy	Since attending TR, I feel better about my future and can see my future.
	I am comfortable introducing myself to others verbally.
	I am comfortable introducing myself to others in writing.
	Since attending TR, when I have a question or need something, I feel more comfortable asking.
Career Pathways	I believe it is important to get to know people who may be helpful to me.
	I have developed and maintained a relationship with a professional in my field of interest.
	I found it beneficial to attend the guest speaker presentations.
	I will recommend TR to those who are interested.
	I have chosen a mentor.
	I have actively pursued placement into a summer job.
	I have secured a summer job.

Data Analysis

We used inductive content analysis, coding notes, classifying the coding, and identifying patterns, categories, and themes (Patton, 2017). Intercoder reliability was established by the two researchers coding individually and then coming together to discuss and establish agreed upon themes as a form of triangulation (Creswell & Poth, 2018). An online qualitative analysis application, Dedoose, was used to organize the analyzed texts relating to each code. Through thematic analysis, three overarching themes emerged from the focus groups and surveys regarding participants' experiences and program impact. These themes were 1) Teen Response program strategies, 2) growth in self-efficacy, and 3) being an advocate for self and others. In this paper, we focus on the essential theme, Teen Response Program Strategies, which included three sub-themes. Data excerpts illustrating each sub-theme are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Themes and Selected Excerpts

Themes	Sub-themes	Student Excerpts
Theme 1: Teen Response Program Strategies	Creating a Safe and Supportive Learning Environment	This program makes me and my sister and brother be stronger. Miss E tells us always to try, not to give up, not to be scared.
		I just did a presentation in Spanish class and I was real nervous and Miss E said don't care about anyone, just do what you want. And the project went well and I didn't shake and I felt comfortable with it.

	Fostering Language Competency	<p>[Student translator]: Before, she did not know what people were talking about. She was scared. She did not know what to say. Now she understands what they're talking and she tries to speak.</p> <p>It was always hard to go to a shop and buy something because I don't know English and I don't know how to say something. I don't know how much I should pay. But now I see the changes in English language. I could go out and buy something.</p>
	Building Cultural Knowledge and Skills in Career Pathways	<p>Before Teen Response, I didn't know anything about being a lawyer. When the lawyers came, they talked about what it's like to be a lawyer and the exams, the challenge. I didn't know that there are different types of lawyers. I learned a lot about it and then I know I want to be a lawyer.</p> <p>Miss E helped me get an interview at Burger King. Before I would not have known what to say but we practiced interviewing. And then when I went for the interview, I was not as nervous and I knew what to say and I knew what to do.</p> <p>TR helped me write a resume. And find a job for the summer...I will work in a flower shop</p>

Findings

The student focus group data suggested that the TR program used several effective strategies to foster student's learning engagement, strengthen their self-efficacy, and develop their career pathways. Three predominant strategies emerged from the data: 1) creating a safe and supportive learning environment, 2) fostering student's language competency, and 3) building student's cultural knowledge and skills in career pathways. These critical strategies are discussed in detail in the following sections.

Creating a Safe and Supportive Learning Environment

The TR program created an atmosphere that was safe, positive, and supportive as indicated by several students. Several student respondents mentioned their great rapport with TR staff and provided specific examples of the support from TR staff. A caring community was established in which both staff and peers were supportive and encouraging of each other; student strengths were identified and built upon; and mistakes turned into positive learning experiences.

The relationship established between program staff and students was one of the most essential ingredients in shaping the caring community. Students provided specific examples of support from TR staff. For example, several students shared the importance of verbal encouragement:

This program makes me and my sister and brother be stronger. Miss E tells us always to try, not to give up, not to be scared.

I just did a presentation in Spanish class and I was real nervous and Miss E said don't care about anyone, just do what you want. And the project went well and I didn't shake and I felt comfortable with it.

Students also provided examples of the nonverbal behavioral support the program staff provided, such as "smiling; happy to see us; gave us hugs." Those gestures had a positive impact.

Trust was well-established in the TR community. Several students described their relationship with the program staff and their TR peers. They referred to them as family. "If you saw what Miss E does for me and my sister and brother, you would think she is part of our family," said a student. Another student pointed out, "[program staff] told me we are like family. You don't need to be scared or shy. That stayed in my mind. This is my second family." It was evident that students felt safe and trusted the program staff.

The program created a caring community of learners who supported each other, fostering their self-efficacy. Students described how they felt about the peer support: "All of us want to know about each other and they always have time for you." Another student stated, "I was shaking to do a presentation because I didn't know English well and I mix up the words. Then I came here and I feel confident. No one laughs at each other because we're all learning English. After my presentation, everyone clapped for me." The safe and supportive environment allowed students to focus on building their English and cultural competency without constantly worrying about the judgement of others.

Fostering Language Competency

Many students stated that their English improved significantly after attending the program, including speaking, listening, and comprehension. Some indicated that they could engage in communication exchanges with others and discussion in class. Additionally, students learned new vocabulary and speaking skills while in the program.

One student shared about her growth in communication and comprehension after attending the TR program, “Before, I did not know what people were talking about. I was scared. I did not know what to say. Now I understand what they’re talking and I try to speak.”

Another student noticed the impact on her daily life through the English language improvement.

It was always hard to go to a shop and buy something because I don’t know English and I don’t know how to say something. I don’t know how much I should pay. But now I see the changes in English language. I could go out and buy something.

Further evidence of language proficiency was seen when comparing students’ average scores on the Ohio English Language Proficiency Assessment (OELPA) between spring of 2018 and spring of 2019. Every student showed improved scores in all areas, including listening, reading, speaking, writing, and composite performance (Teen Response, 2019). These improvements are in alignment with the student respondents’ reporting regarding their English proficiency level.

Building Cultural Knowledge and Skills in Career Pathways

TR offered guest speaker sessions, inviting 25 community professionals from various career fields to introduce their professions and discuss their career pathways. Based on the survey, most students (90%) found the sessions very helpful. As one student said,

Before Teen Response, I didn’t know anything about being a lawyer. When the lawyers came, they talked about what it’s like to be a lawyer and the exams, the challenge. I didn’t know that there are different types of lawyers. I learned a lot about it and then I know I want to be a lawyer.

The guest speaker sessions helped students understand necessary steps on the pathway toward specific careers. This understanding motivated and assisted these teenagers in developing a Personal Development Plan (PDP) for their future career pathways. Guest speakers also provided career relevant knowledge and skills in the workplace. One student explained, “I’ve met with people, important people.... We learned that we need to meet with the manager. We learned about the questions they will ask us.”

The TR program fostered students’ capacities in career relevant fundamental skills, such as resume writing, interviewing, professional behavior, etc. The program offered mock interview sessions for students to practice interview skills and prepare them for future interview opportunities. The TR program also connected students with job opportunities. This is evident in the focus group excerpt below:

Miss E helped me get an interview at Burger King. Before I would not have known what to say but we practiced interviewing. And then when I went for the interview, I was not as nervous and I knew what to say and I knew what to do.

Students indicated that communication and interaction were networking tools that could lead to opportunities. Being taught how to effectively communicate with professionals was essential to student growth in the program. Searching for a summer internship, a student independently contacted a guest speaker’s law firm and inquired about summer job opportunities. This interaction would not have been likely to occur at the start of the TR program as self-efficacy and self-advocacy concerning career goals had not yet been developed.

As expressed in the excerpts above, participants recognized the value of the TR program. Several students felt strongly that the program should be made available in other schools so that it could benefit more students. Ninety-five percent of the survey participants indicated they would recommend the TR program to others.

Recommendations

The findings of the surveys and focus groups yielded further discussion and recommendations for future iterations of the TR initiative centered on program development. Two areas specifically addressed in the paragraphs below are timeline and length of support services.

Timeline

The research revealed that students needed support from adults and peers. Social interactions play a vital role in fostering student self-efficacy and creating a sense of belonging, which is especially important for adolescent self-identity development (Guan & So, 2016; Liu & Ngai, 2020; Schwartz & Petrova, 2018). We recommend the program participant recruitment and youth activities be launched the summer before the start of the new school year. This way, students will have the opportunity to build rapport with peers in the program as well as program staff and gain knowledge and skills pertinent to entering a new year in high school.

Length of Support

Based on the data collected, it was clear that student participants spoke highly of the TR program and noted its impact. They indicated that the program helped them stay engaged in school and foster their cultural knowledge and skills in language, social interactions, and education and career pathways. The students envisioned the program continuing services for incoming ninth graders, as well as gaining the additional capacity to provide continuous support for past participants.

From its inception, TR was intended to be a 4-year program, serving youth from 9th through 12th grade. The research conducted on the pilot program underscores the notion that students would benefit from additional TR support in the summer prior school year. As TR entered its second year, services were offered through the

summer, though distinct from those during the school year. Summer support is focused on supporting students' summer job engagement. These experiences allow students to apply the skills and knowledge they acquired during their first-year experience and continue building on them throughout their educational careers.

As to the level of scaffolding, we believe students would benefit from a more gradual reduction of support as the responsibility of navigating educational and career pathways shifts from school personnel to adolescent refugees. Further, we envision second-year participants assuming mentorship roles for incoming first-year students with additional opportunities to apply the skills and knowledge they have acquired during their first-year experience in TR.

Conclusion

Due to ongoing conflicts, climate change, and poverty, millions of children and youth continue to be displaced worldwide. There is a lack of research focused on adolescent refugee programs. More studies need to be undertaken to understand the programs that currently exist. Research such as ours conducted with the participants of Teen Response is crucial because it identifies effective practices and strategies that can be replicated by others working with this population. Investing in refugee adolescents by providing them with the tools and knowledge to launch healthy and productive lives leads to communities enriched by cultural diversity and economic stimulation. These relationships have the potential to be mutually beneficial for all.

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Author Information

Grace H. C. Huang, Ph.D.

Associate Professor, Department of Teacher Education
Cleveland State University
2121 Euclid Ave., Cleveland OH 44115
(216) 523-7118

Monica Miller Marsh, Ph.D.

Associate Professor & Executive Director, Kent State University Child Development Center
Kent State University
775 Loop Rd., Kent OH 44242
(330) 672-2559

Naila Asad Paul

Director of Youth Programs
The Refugee Response
2054 W.47 St, Cleveland, OH 44102
